

A Pre-Experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Self Structured Teaching Program on Knowledge Regarding Good Touch and Bad Touch Among Children of Primary School at Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh

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Abstract: The current study aimed to assess the effectiveness of self-structured teaching program on knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among children of Primary School at Bilaspur Chhattisgarh pre-experimental research design is utilized to achieve the stated. **Objectives:** 1. To assess the pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding good touch and bad touch among children. 2. To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among children. 3. To find out the association between post-test knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch and selected socio-demographic variables of the children. **Hypothesis:** H1: There will be a significant increased post test knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among primary school children of Bilaspur (C.G.). H2: There will be significant association between post- test knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch with selected socio demographic variables of the primary school children. **Major finding of the study:** Study reveals that there was a significant difference between pre test – post test knowledge score regarding good touch and bad touch among children of primary school children pre test reveals that majority of subject 72% (72) have inadequate knowledge, 28% (28) have moderate knowledge & 0% (0) have adequate knowledge. In post test majority of subjects 58% (58) have adequate knowledge, 42% (42) have moderate knowledge & none of them have inadequate knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch. The overall mean, mean percentage of pre test score is 5.89 (5.89%) with standard deviation 2.083 & overall mean, mean percentage of post test score is 12.62 (12.62%) with standard deviation 3.106. the effectiveness of self-structured teaching program was significant. Difference between pre test and post level of knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among children of primary school as calculated “Z-test” value 18.69 was greater than the table value 0.0202 at 0.05 level of significance, hence it was effective. Chi-square was calculated to find out the association between the post test score of primary school children with their selected socio demographic variables. It reveals that there was a significant association found between the post test scores of knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch like family structured. There was no significant association found between post test scores of knowledge level with socio demographic variables such as gender, education.

Keywords: Self Structured Teaching, Good Touch, Bad Touch.

1. Introduction

TOUCH is a positive experience that gives a safe feeling from the loved one. Good touch gives reinforcement and it is essential for health and good behavior. Bad touch is unsafe and can also lead to psychiatric disorders, any secret touch or touch to their private part.

Good touch and bad touch are words mainly used to explain which touch is safe and not safe. A good touch is always a sense of care, affection, love, and help. It will not make an uncomfortable experience for the child. A bad touch is something you don't want and that makes you feel uncomfortable.

Childhood is the most important stage in the development cycle. The reported child abuse incidences are increasing day by day. Each abuse against children has a negative impact on the victim's physical health. During childhood, the acquire more knowledge from their surroundings. Good touch and bad touch are learned through their day-to-day activity.

2. Methodology

Organization of Data Section I: Distribution of subjects according to socio demographic variables in frequency & percentage.

Section II: (A) Assessment of pre test – Post test knowledge score regarding good touch and bad touch through mean, mean percentage, mean difference, standard deviation & criteria analysis of pre test & post test level of knowledge score by frequency & percentage.

Section II: (B) Critical analysis of pre test and post test level knowledge score by frequency and percentage.

Section III: Evaluation of data related to effectiveness of self-structure teaching program on knowledge regarding good touch

and bad touch using “Z -Test”.

Section IV: Association between selected Socio demographic Variables with post test knowledge of primary School children regarding good touch and bad touch using “Chi Square Test.”

Fig. 1. Methodology

The analysis of data was organized and presented under the following heading:

Section-I: Distribution of Subjects According to Socio Demographic Variables in Frequency & Percentage

The majority of children 39% (39) belong to the age group of 10-11 years, 34% (34) belongs to age group of 9-10 years, 27% (27) belongs to age group of 8-9 years. majority of subjects 68% (68) are female and 38% (38) are male. majority of students are 5th class 39% (39), and 4th class is 34% (34) and 3rd class are 27% (27). majority of students are nuclear family 36% (36), joint family 36% (36) and extended family 28% (28). majority of subject 44% (44) are farmer, 40% (40) private employee and govt. employee 16% (16). majority of subject 56% (56) are house wife, 27% (27) private employee and govt. employee 17% (16). majority of subject 72% (72) were not having knowledge and 28% (28) had some knowledge. majority of subject were source of information from parents 12% (12), grandparents 6% (6), sibling 6% (6), other source 5% (5).

Section II: Assessment of Pre Test – Post Test Knowledge Score Regarding Good Touch and Bad Touch Through Total Mean, Mean Percentage, Mean Difference, Standard Deviation & Criteria Analysis of Pre Test & Post Test Level of Knowledge Score by Frequency & Percentage.

A. Assessment of knowledge score regarding good touch and bad touch between pre test – post test through mean, mean percentage, mean difference & standard deviation

The knowledge of pre test and post test was 589 and 1252 respectively out of 1800. The total mean of pre test is 5.89 & mean percentage is 5.89%, total mean of post test is 12.62 & mean percentage is 12.62%. The standard deviation of pre test was 2.09 and post test 3.10 and mean difference of pre test & post test is 7.31.

B. Criteria Analysis of pre test and post test level of knowledge score by frequency and percentage

The knowledge score between pre test and post test. Where, in pre test majority of subjects 72% (72) have inadequate knowledge, 28% (28) have moderate knowledge & 0% (0) have adequate knowledge. In post test majority of subjects 58% (58) have adequate knowledge, 42% (42) have moderate knowledge & none of them have inadequate knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch.

So H_1 hypothesis is accepted with regards to knowledge There is significant increased post – test knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among primary school children at Bilaspur (C.G.).

Section III: Evaluation of Data Related to Effectiveness of Self Structured Teaching Program on Knowledge Regarding Good Touch and Bad Touch Using Z – Test

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Z - Test evaluates the effectiveness of self-structured teaching program on knowledge good touch and bad touch

The effectiveness of self-structured teaching program that increases the knowledge is greater than the table value at (18.69 > 0.0202) at the 0.05 level of significant. It shows that the self-structured teaching program was very effective in the term of gain in knowledge regarding good touch and bad touch among children of government Primary School Mopka Bilaspur Chhattisgarh.

Section IV: Association Between Selected Socio Demographic Variables with Post Test Knowledge of Primary School Children Regarding Good Touch and Bad Touch, Using – Chi Square Test

Chi – square was calculated to find out the association between the post test scores of children with their selected demographic variables. It reveals that there was a significant association found between the post scores of good touch and bad touch and demographic variables like age, family structure.

There was no significant association found between post test scores of knowledge level when compared to other demographic variables such as gender, education,

Hence H_2 is accepted. There is significant association

between post test knowledge, regarding good touch and bad touch in primary school children with their selected demographic variables

3. Conclusion

Based on the finding mean post test knowledge level was higher than the mean pre test knowledge level. This result indicates self-structured teaching program was found to be significantly effective in improving the knowledge level of the primary school children regarding good touch and bad touch.

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